

Influence of Surface Active Agents on the Crystallisation Kinetics under different Stirring Conditions

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The effects of sodium dodecyl benzene sulphonate as surface active agent on crystallisation kinetics have been studied in a 'continuously mixed suspension mixed product removal evaporative crystalliser' (MSMPRC). Mechanical stirring as well as air stirring are separately tested and their relative effects discussed. The nucleation rate is substantially higher in the presence of surface active agents for air stirring than that for mechanical stirring under identical conditions. The growth rates are observed to be nearly the same for two types of stirring.

Chemical additives are often used to suppress or promote nucleation rate, growth rate and crystal habit. Many authors¹ studied the effects of additive on the crystallisation kinetics. Their results are used to examine the simultaneous effects of chemical modifier on crystal nucleation, growth rate and habit for mechanical stirring. It is well established that one of the main factors which determines the crystal size distribution in an industrial crystalliser is crystallisation kinetics. It is therefore convenient to use the kinetic parameters to model the nucleation kinetics as a function of operating conditions in an attempt to derive scale-up rules for industrial application.

The object of this work is to study the effect of surface active agent on the crystallisation kinetics using two types of stirring.

Theory of determination of kinetics parameters: A balance on the number of crystals per unit volume in a perfect crystalliser at steady state (neither breakage or agglomeration to occur) leads to the form,

$$d(nG)/dL + n/T = 0 \quad (1)$$

which on integration can be represented as

$$n = n^{\circ} \exp(-L/GT) \quad (2)$$

or

$$\log(n) = \log(n^{\circ}) - L/GT \quad (3)$$

Thus the relation between $\log(n)$ and L is a straight-line with a slope and intercept of $\log(n^{\circ})$. From the

slope and residence time, the growth rate (G) was calculated. The nucleation rate (B) on the other hand, can be calculated from the definition of the population density. The total number of crystal in unit volume of a system is given as

$$N = \int_0^{\infty} n dL \quad (4)$$

but

$$B = [dN/dT]_{L \rightarrow 0} = [(dN/dL)(dL/dT)]_{L \rightarrow 0} \quad (5)$$

From equations (5) and (2),

$$dN/dL = [(d(ndL)/dL)]_{L \rightarrow 0} = [d(n \exp -L/GT)dL/dL]_{L \rightarrow 0} = n^{\circ} \quad (6)$$

$$B = n^{\circ}G \quad (7)$$

The parameters are related to the crystallisation rates operative in the system. The rates derive from the fundamental kinetic laws for nucleation and growth and the constraints imposed on the system, i.e. system parameters such as concentration of additive, degree of stirring, and energy input or removal rate.

Results and Discussion

Values of the system used and the model parameters at various concentrations of the additive for air and mechanical stirring are shown in Table 1.

The best way of representing the effect of the additive on the crystal growth rate is by means of a suitable

mathematical equations²,

$$G = G(S) \exp (b C) \tag{8}$$

or

$$\log (G) = \log (G(S)) + b C \tag{9}$$

If the values of $\log (G)$ are plotted against concentration of the additive (C), a straight line is obtained, the slope of which can be used to obtain the constant b

TABLE 1 - SYSTEM AND MODEL PARAMETERS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF SURFACE ACTIVE AGENT (AIR AND MECHANICAL STIRRING)

Run	I s	C ppm	$\times 10^{-8} G$ m s ⁻¹	$\times 10^{14} n$ m ⁴	M kg m ³	$\times 10^6 B$ m ³ s ⁻¹
Air stirring						
1	2049	0	11.02	1.21	63.1	13.33
2	2152	5	9.30	1.96	63.0	18.25
3	1010	10	9.01	32.00	44.0	20.25
4	1365	8	8.01	25.28	72.0	31.00
5	2280	10	7.86	3.05	63.2	24.93
6	2378	15	6.63	5.13	64.0	33.96
7	2488	20	5.61	8.30	63.3	46.45
8	2572	25	4.73	14.47	63.4	63.55
9	2701	30	4.10	21.23	63.2	86.96
Mechanical stirring			$\times 10^{13} n$ (m ⁴)			
1	1531	0.0	10.10	6.288	72.0	6.350
2	1617	5.0	9.14	7.530	72.01	6.881
3	1721	8.0	8.01	5.010	36.05	4.008
4	2355	10.0	6.00	10.000	79.00	6.000
5	1799	10.0	7.598	10.002	71.90	7.600
6	2043	15.0	6.314	13.303	72.30	8.320
7	2298	20.0	5.248	17.340	71.90	9.100
8	2568	25.0	4.364	22.820	72.00	9.960
9	2891	30.0	3.620	30.110	71.85	10.900

and the intercept representing the growth rate without additive. Also the values (b) for two types of stirring can be calculated by using regression analysis. On the other hand the nucleation rate can be viewed through the semi-empirical correlation

$$B = k G^i M^j \exp (d C) \tag{10}$$

To determine the exponents and constant in equation (10) multiple regression analysis can be used. To do this equation (10) can be rewritten in the form

$$\log (B) = \log (k) + i \log (G) + j \log (M) + d C \tag{11}$$

Computer regression analysis of the data using equations (9) and (11) yielded the values of the exponents and the constants (Table 2)

TABLE 2

	Equation (9)	Equation (11)			
	b	k	i	j	d
Mechanical stirring	-0.035	8.33×10^{18}	2.0	1.001	0.092
Air stirring	-0.033	6.14×10^{20}	2.0	0.16	0.130

The final form of the correlations is thus as follows

For mechanical stirring

$$G = G(S) \exp(-0.035 C) \tag{12}$$

$$B = 8.33 \times 10^{16} G^{2.0} M^{1.01} \exp(0.035 C) \tag{13}$$

For air stirring

$$G = G(S) \exp(-0.033 C) \tag{14}$$

$$B = 6.14 \times 10^{20} G^{2.0} M^{0.14} \exp(0.16 C) \tag{15}$$

To test the validity of equations (13) and (15) the values of B can be plotted against the product of the variables which give straight lines showing the validity of the correlation. The slopes of these straight lines represent the values of k , which are 8.33×10^{18} for mechanical stirring and 6.14×10^{20} in case of air stirring.

Equations (12) and (14) show that the growth rates are related to the surface active agent concentration by a negative exponential of argument. The physical concept to explain this is that of the surface active agent is adsorbed at the crystal surface and adsorption on certain sites in growing crystal results in the reduction of the growth rate. On the other hand the nucleation is increased by increasing the surface active agent concentration (positive exponential argument, equations 13 and 15). This is due to inhibition of the crystal growth rate in the presence of surfactant, which increases the level of supersaturation leading to increase in the nucleation rate. Equations (13) and (15) show that the effect of the surface active agent concentration on the nucleation rate in the case of air stirring is higher than that

in the case of mechanical stirring, the interpretation of this phenomenon is that the air bubble diameter is decreased by increasing the concentration of surfactant. The diameter of the bubble can be computed by equating the buoyancy force on the immersed bubble $[(\pi/6) d_b^3 \rho]$ which tends to lift the bubble away from the orifice, to the force $[\pi d \sigma]$ due to surface tension, which tends to retain it at bubbler.

This provides the following equation,

$$d_b = (6 d \sigma / g \rho)^{1/3} \quad (16)$$

From equation (16), it is clear that decreasing the surface tension by increasing the surfactant concentration, the bubble diameter decreased, consequently, the interfacial area between air and solution also increased. On the other hand, the rate of evaporation (R_v) is a function of contact surface (A) between air and solution relating to the following equation³,

$$R_v = K A (H_s - H) \quad (17)$$

According to equation (17), the surface active agent is an essential factor effecting the rate of evaporation. But the mass transfer coefficient (K) decreased as the interfacial tension is reduced. The net result is a decreased rate of mass transfer. It was unable to detect the retardation in the rate of evaporation of water. This observation was investigated by many authors⁴. But heterogeneous nucleation is generally rapidly increased with increasing interfacial surface area between air and solution, and the rate of homogeneous nucleation is related to surface tension by the relationship⁵,

$$B = a(S) \exp[-b \sigma / \log S]^2 \quad (18)$$

As a consequence, the rate of nucleation is very rapidly increased and the product is finer. This is the physical concept behind the much faster increase of nucleation rate in case of air stirring.

Conclusion : Surface active agent inhibited the growth rate and enhanced the nucleation rate for both types of stirring and could be incorporated into the power-law with a positive exponential in terms of ppm of modifier. Comparative study of these correlations lead to the following conclusion : (i) the growth rates to the surfactant concentration by negative exponential are nearly the same for the two types of stirring, and (ii) a comparison between the nucleation rates for the JICS-6

two types of stirring in the presence of surfactant shows that the nucleation rate in the case of air stirring is much higher than that in case of mechanical stirring

The study demonstrates the utility of controlling the nucleation rate and the growth rate by addition of surface active agent as a modifier.

Experimental

Evaporation crystallisation of sodium chloride was selected as a system exhibiting a flat solubility curve. Sodium dodecylbenzene sulphonate was used as the surface active agent. Schematic diagram of the system and the apparatus used in this study (Fig. 1) has been described in detail elsewhere⁶

Fig. 1. (A) Schematic diagram of crystalliser. (1) saturator, (2) rotameter, (3) crystalliser, (4) filter, (5) pump, (6) heating element, (7) regulated by-pass tank to steady state, (8) reservoir.

(B) Mechanical crystalliser.

(C) Air crystalliser : (1) rotameter, (2) thermometer, (3) electrical heater, (4) control, (5) relay

Procedure : The crystalliser was fed continuously with a saturated solution of NaCl from a saturator at 50° in which a predetermined amount of surface active agent was well mixed, the range of concentration of the surfactant being 0.0–30 ppm. After steady state was achieved, the suspension-solution was withdrawn from the crystalliser. It was filtered, dried and sieved Val-

ues of n and L were calculated as shown in the appendix. In case of air stirring, a foaming was observed and which increased as a result of the presence of surface active agent. A few drops of kerosene was added as an antifoam agent. Agglomeration of crystals from the product was eliminated due to the assumption of equation (1)

Appendix

Calculation of population density, n , :

$$dM = \rho k n L^3 dL$$

by integration over the range L_1 to L_2 , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \bar{\rho} k n \bar{L}^3 (L_1 - L_2) \\ &= \bar{\rho} k n L^3 \Delta L \end{aligned}$$

but

$$M_{L_1, L_2} = M \phi_{L_1, L_2}$$

where, $[\phi_{L_1, L_2}]$ is the fraction of crystals by weight retained in the aperture L_2 and passed from the screen aperture L_1 . M_{L_1, L_2} is the magma density in the range of crystal size, L_1 to L_2 , and L the average diameter $[L_1 + L_2]/2$

Therefore,

$$n = M \phi_{L_1, L_2} / \bar{\rho} k \bar{L}^3 \Delta L$$

According to the dimension used in the text, the above value of n must be multiplied by 10^{24} , and therefore,

$$n = (M \phi / (\bar{\rho} k \bar{L}^3 \Delta L)) \times 10^{24}$$

Nomenclature

B	Nucleation rate, $m^3 s^{-1}$
G	Growth rate, $m s^{-1}$
i, j, b, d	Parameters in equations (9) and (11)
L	Characteristic crystal dimension, m
M	Suspension density, $kg m^{-3}$
n	Population density, m^{-4}

n^o	Population density at zero crystal size, m^{-4}
N	Total number of crystals in a unit volume defined in equation (4),
T	Residence time, s
H	Humidity of air, $kg kg^{-1}$
H_s	Humidity of air at saturation condition, $kg kg^{-1}$
ρ	Density of solution, $kg m^{-3}$
ρ	Density of solid crystal, $kg m^{-3}$
σ	Surface tension, $N m^{-1}$
d_p	Diameter of bubble, m
d	Diameter of bubbler, m
R	Rate of evaporation, $kg s^{-1}$
K	Mass transfer coefficient, $kg s^{-1} m^{-2}$
k	Shape volume, m^3
$a(S), b$	Parameter in equation (18)
S	Supersaturation, $kg m^{-1}$
A	Interfacial surface area, m^2
$G(S)$	Growth rate without additive, $m s^{-1}$

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